

STUDIES ON GUM JEOL (*ODINA WODIER*, ROXB.). PART I.

SOLUTION AND PURIFICATION

BY S. N. MUKHERJEE AND GOBINDALAL BANERJEE

Different samples of gum jeol, both old and freshly collected, have been tested for their miscibility with water and a method of purification for the same has been worked out by precipitation with alcohol. Freshly collected samples have been found to be readily miscible with water. Immiscibility with water is attributed not so much to the state of dehydration of the older samples as much to their age.

The gum is an indigenous product in many parts of India and is obtained as an exudate from plants commonly known in Bengal as Jeol trees (*Odina wodier*, Roxb.). Practically no work on this gum is to be found in the literature excepting the little recorded by Watt ("Dictionary of Economic Products of India"). This gum is used in many parts of India as a nutritive food specially after the puerperal period of women. The growing importance of the gum in commerce and industry justifies a thorough investigation into its physical and chemical behaviours. The present series of work embodies the results of such investigations. Work on the solution and purification of the gum has been taken up in this part to guide selection of samples, method of solution and purification and other conditions of experimentation.

The following samples of crude gum jeol were procured for examination. The samples were mostly collected from plants in October after the rains were over.

Sample 1. A freshly exuded semi-solid mass of brown colour, almost jelly-like in appearance, directly from plants.

Sample 2. A deep brown, old, air-dried sample, collected from the plant in the previous year after rains and preserved in a bottle.

Sample 3. A deep brown solid directly from the plant, collected in December.

Sample 4. Similar to sample 3.

Sample 5. A fresh semi-solid brownish black sample, collected in October from a different locality.

Sample 6. An old, grey, powdery mass, purchased from the local market.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the samples contained considerable amounts of impurities which usually consisted of bark and leaves of plants, in some cases earthy matter and in one instance, probably some putrefied gum. These foreign matters were fortunately found to be insoluble in water and alcohol, the latter being the common precipitant for purification of the gum. An approximate but comparative estimate of the non-volatile impurities present was made by determination of the ash contents in the crude specimens mentioned above (Table I) and

comparing these with the ash contents of some of the purified samples (Table II). The actual determination was made by slow incineration of known weights of the air-dried gum in platinum crucibles.

TABLE I

Sample No.	Weight taken.	Total ash obtained.	Ash %.	Mean value.
1*	6.12 g.	0.2754 g.	4.5	4.33%
	5.01	0.2015	4.2	
	4.10	0.1863	4.3	
2	4.20	0.1723	4.1	4.43
	4.51	0.2120	4.7	
	3.60	0.1712	4.5	
6	4.30	0.1375	3.20	3.26
	5.15	0.1572	3.02	
	3.19	0.1124	3.55	

Solution and Purification

Different samples of the crude gum were found not to go into solution in water easily. They thus offered a point of contrast with gum arabic (*Acacia arabica*) which would dissolve much more rapidly. Solubility of the different samples appeared to be different. The samples in the following discussion have been divided into three categories in each of which were noticed some peculiar features of interest.

Samples 1 and 5.—Both of them were brown, semi-solid, viscous masses freshly collected from the plants. Both of them were miscible with water in all proportions leaving the insoluble matters in gum as the only residue.

Purification of sample 1 was carried out according to the following procedure. About 5 g. of the crude gum were mixed with 15 c. c. of water (approx.), stirred well till the gum dissolved, and the solution filtered through filter paper. Filtration was slow and was interrupted by frequent choking of the filter papers which were therefore repeatedly renewed. Small amount of alcohol (2 c. c.) was then added to 10 c. c. of the filtrate, when a white viscous mass immediately came down, but on shaking this precipitate dissolved again. With addition of further amounts of alcohol (about 50% by volume) it was found that the precipitate no longer dissolved on shaking and the supernatant liquid suddenly became clearer. The precipitated mass, which was perfectly white and granular when first formed, gradually changed to a grey colour within a short time simultaneously settling to a sticky mass which could not be suspended again in the supernatant liquid. It has been observed as a matter of experience that when such a phenomenon occurs (the supernatant solution

* Sample 1 was, however, freed from moisture before incineration (as originally it was a semi-solid mass) by heating over a water-bath for 4 to 5 hours and keeping subsequently in a CaCl_2 -desiccator for 4 or 5 days till constant weight.

became clear and the precipitated gum sticky) this is an indication that the maximum amount of gum has precipitated out. The yield of the purified product after two such treatments with alcohol was about 60% as determined by separating the gum and carefully drying the same to a constant weight. The purified product was found to yield 2.7% of ash against 4.3% observed with the crude sample (Table II). Sample 5 also behaved similarly. The observations on both these samples appear in Table II.

TABLE II

Sample No.	Yield after twice precipitated with alcohol (approx.).	Ash content of samples	
		Purified.	Crude.
1	60%	2.7%	4.3%
5	55	3.1	5.5

Samples 3 and 4.—The samples were in the form of lumps. They were taken as such and mixed with 25 times their weight of double distilled water, previously sterilised by prolonged boiling and the mixture was preserved in bottles under toluene (pure, B. D. H.). The lumps did not readily mix with water but swelled more and more till the whole volume of the liquid was occupied. This took about 10 to 12 days' time for each sample. The solution had a brown colour and was transparent. Insoluble matters, mostly leaves, barks, etc., formed a compact scum on the surface which could be removed without any difficulty. This solution was dilute and it yielded about 5 to 6 g. of purified gum from about 50 g. of the crude sample in presence of approximately 80% of alcohol. A more concentrated solution (10 g. of gum in 100 c. c. water) could be prepared with these samples but a longer period of time (about 15-20 days) was necessary for the complete mixing of the gum with water. A dilute solution of the gum could, however, be concentrated by evaporation at ordinary temperature only under reduced pressure but not at high temperature, since the gum appears to be hydrolysed when the temperature is high (vide Part II of this series).

Samples 2 and 6.—Both of them were air-dried samples. About 25 g. of each sample, powdered in a mortar, were separately mixed with about 150 c. c. of water in two Jena bottles. The gums were found not to mix with water even by violent shaking with a mechanical stirrer for 10 to 12 hours. The major portion in both samples remained in a swollen state. The swollen mass and the dilute solution formed two distinct layers, the latter being on the top. The two layers did not mix even on keeping for two weeks. This evidently suggested that either the layers were in equilibrium or that the passage of one into the other was a very slow process. In the case of sample 2, it was observed that after a period of four months and a half the two layers disappeared and a homogeneous solution was formed. Sample 6 required longer time (about 6 months)

Both the layers (10 c. c.) in each sample were separately pipetted out and treated with absolute alcohol. It was observed that the upper layer in each case yielded no precipitate but only a slight turbidity even though the resulting concentration of alcohol was brought up to as much as 85%. The lower layer (swollen gum), however, yielded the precipitated gum in almost the original crude form having a thick brown colour when the concentration of alcohol was about 20%. It appeared that the phenomenon was due to the removal of water from the swollen gum by the added alcohol. No purified gum could, however, be obtained from these samples.

D I S C U S S I O N

The different samples of the gum available for these investigations can thus be differentiated into three categories, as mentioned above, according to the age of the samples. The solubility behaviour differs in these three categories quite markedly. The greater the age of a sample, the lower is its solubility in water. Sample 2, which was known to be old and sample 6, which was obtained from the local market and whose age could not therefore be ascertained but which was undoubtedly very old as judged by its physical appearance, were the most insoluble among all the samples examined.

From the above observations at first it appeared that solubility depended on the loss of water on the part of the sample due to age and the drier a sample, the more insoluble it would be. This point was, however, further investigated by drying sample 1 on a thermostat slowly at 66°. This operation required about 7 days for completion. The solid thus obtained practically exhibited no difference in behaviour from the semi-solid parent body (sample 1) so far as its solubility was concerned. Age which was the only other alternative therefore appeared to be the determining factor in the difference in behaviour of the different samples. The yield of the purified product and the amount of alcohol necessary for its precipitation also appeared to depend on the age of the gum. If the sample be fresh and the concentration of the gum in solution be moderate (5-7%) then the concentration of alcohol necessary and sufficient for complete precipitation is about 50-60% and the yield is also about 60%. With moderately old samples concentration of alcohol found suitable for precipitation was about 70 to 80% and the yield 10% only. With very old samples two distinct layers appeared, one being a dilute solution which yielded almost no precipitate with alcohol. The second layer contained the swollen gum which precipitated readily with alcohol but did not yield pure products. The impurities were not eliminated.

Another observation in this connection was that in almost every case when the solution was not freshly prepared and/or the solution preserved for some time and then treated with alcohol the precipitated gum was not sticky in the beginning but became sticky when kept in contact with the mother-liquor for a day or two.

C O N C L U S I O N S

To sum up the experience gathered in the preparation of a solution of this gum and its purification is that fresh samples obtained in the semi-solid state from the plant are the best to work with. When samples become dried up in air and become old they undergo marked decrease in solubility and the yield of the precipitated gum is also small. If the sample is fresh and soft, the purified gum obtained after precipitation by alcohol is fairly white in colour and the colour does not change easily. The aqueous solution from a white specimen of the purified gum is also colourless.

Soft and fresh samples of the gum, directly collected from a plant in the month of October after the rains were over (in Bengal), were therefore always used in the investigations recorded in subsequent parts of this series of study.

Our best thanks are due to Dr. J. N. Mukherjee, D. Sc., F. N. I., C. B. E., Director, Indian Agricultural Research Institute for his keen interest and valuable suggestions in connection with this work and to Dr. D. Chakravarti of the University College of Science for his kind co-operation.

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Received October 11, 1947.

STUDIES ON GUM JEOL (*ODINA WODIER*, ROXB.). PART II.

HYDROLYSIS AND THE REDUCING SUGARS

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Gum jeol has been hydrolysed by H_2SO_4 (conc. $<0.5N$) to yield some reducing substances and a complex acid (termed *jeolic acid*) which forms colloidal solution in water. More drastic hydrolysis of the gum with H_2SO_4 (conc. $>1.5N$) by prolonged refluxing for 16 to 18 hours yields larger amounts of reducing substances, being about 86% (calculated as glucose) of the weight of the gum. These reducing substances have been identified and characterised as *l*-arabinose and *d*-galactose.

In Part I of this series of investigations (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25, 59) it has been observed that fresh gums, specially when collected in the semi-solid state, are readily miscible in water but, an old dry sample is only slightly miscible. This latter when kept in contact with water for a number of days gives a uniform solution. This naturally raises a question as to whether the gum in prolonged contact with water is changed by hydrolysis before passing into solution. In the present investigation an answer to this question has been attempted.